

MULTI-SCALE MODELING OF THE VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF NON-WOVEN, THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

S. Fliegner^{1*}, D. Elmer², T. Seifert², M. Luke¹

¹ Fraunhofer Institute for Mechanics of Materials, Freiburg, Germany

² University of Applied Sciences, Offenburg, Germany

* sascha.fliegner@iw.fraunhofer.de

Keywords: *viscoelastic properties, long fiber reinforced thermoplastics*

1 Introduction

At recent times, the demand of high performing but economically producible lightweight materials for automotive applications is growing. Long fiber reinforced thermoplastics (LFT) can meet these criteria if the part design is reasonably adapted to the respective load cases. In order to fully enable the material's potential in lightweight construction and to take advantage of the basically good strength to density ratio, an appropriate dimensioning is mandatory to avoid large safety factors which would reduce the advantage over traditional construction materials. Hence the complete process chain of the parts produced by injection or compression molding has to be taken into account as the resulting mechanical properties strongly depend on the microstructure which itself is influenced by the local flow field during fabrication and so the part geometry in the end. If significant static loads are present, the creep behavior of the composite must be accounted for which depends together with stiffness and strength on the complex microstructure of the material. In this work, the viscoelastic properties of the pure polypropylene matrix determined from creep tests of substance specimens are implemented into a microstructural finite element (FE) simulation of the composite and the results are compared to those of experimental creep tests of LFT specimens. Thus, the effective viscoelastic behavior for a realistic microstructure based on measured fiber orientation and length distributions can be determined and compared to virtual materials with different fiber length while keeping the orientation and volume content almost constant. This improves the understanding of the material in general and the role of fiber length in particular. Additionally, the homogenization procedure by microstructural simulation, which is essential for process chain based component assessment, can be validated.

2 Methods

2.1 Microstructure generation

The applied structure generation method was presented in [1]. A custom made software tool creates a stack of fibers which correspond to the given fiber orientation distribution (FOD) and fiber length distribution (FLD). The FOD of a characteristic LFT specimen was extracted from computer tomographic scans whereas the FLD was determined by an automated analysis procedure applied on the diluted fiber lattice of an incinerated specimen. The volume fraction was calculated from mass flow values of the LFT fabrication procedure. The generated fiber stack is then compressed by a FE simulation and fiber waviness develops due to the contact between the fibers.

As soon as the desired value for fiber volume fraction (v_f) is reached, the deformed fiber mesh is placed into a cuboid frame which forms the border of the representative volume element (RVE) and the remaining gaps are filled with elements representing the matrix.

Fig. 1 and 2 show an exemplary RVE while the generation procedure is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 1. RVE (dimensions 5 x 5 x 0.16 mm³)

Fig. 2. Mesh detail (dimensions 1 x 1 x 0.1 mm³)

Fig. 3. Microstructure generation procedure presented in [1]

2.2 Modeling of viscoelasticity

The contribution of the glass fibers to the time-dependent deformation behavior of the composite is neglected. They are given time-independent, isotropic elastic properties. The polypropylene matrix is represented by the Burgers model (Fig. 4) to describe a viscoelastic, time-dependent isotropic response. The model consists of a Maxwell (spring and dashpot in series) and a Kelvin-Voigt

element (spring and dashpot parallel) and therefore features the behavior of a fluid (Maxwell) as well as a solid (Kelvin-Voigt) which is characteristic for an ideal thermoplastic material. After the relaxation of the Kelvin-Voigt element, the model exhibits a stationary creep rate depicted by the free dashpot. This is in accordance to the assumption that under constant load, the polymeric chains of an ideal thermoplastic can slip and unfold until infinite time due to the missing side chain network of a thermoset. Equation (1) shows the time-dependent strain for the uniaxial load case under a constant stress σ_0 .

Fig. 4. Rheological notation of the Burgers model

$$\varepsilon = \sigma_0 \left[\frac{1}{E_0} + \frac{t}{\eta_0} + \frac{1}{E_1} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{E_1}{\eta_1} t} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

In order to generalize the model to a three dimensional formulation, both shear and bulk parts of viscoelastic deformation are assumed to be time-dependent and so the Poisson's ratio remains constant over time. The incremental formulation of the model is taken from [2] and [3], as well as a recursive algorithm based on viscoelastic hereditary integrals which is used for the numerical efficient implementation by means of a user subroutine UMAT into the FE code ABAQUS® 6.11. Thus, large RVE structures with up to 10 million elements can be analyzed in a reasonable time.

The four parameters E_0 , E_1 , η_0 , η_1 of the original model remain constant describing linear viscoelastic behavior. This does not match the experimental data which exhibits strong stress dependence. As consequence the model was modified to a stress-dependent formulation to account for the observed nonlinear viscoelastic behavior. The parameters E_1 , η_0 , η_1 of the modified Burgers model become functions of an indicator stress σ_{ind} which is defined by condition (2),

$$\sigma_{ind} = \begin{cases} \sigma_M & \text{if } \sigma_M > |\sigma_P| \\ |\sigma_P| & \text{if } |\sigma_P| > \sigma_M \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

with σ_M being the v. Mises equivalent stress and σ_p the hydrostatic pressure. Outside the experimentally investigated range from 2.5 to 12.5 MPa, linear viscoelasticity is assumed and E_1 , η_0 , η_1 are kept constant. The stiffness of the free spring E_0 is always kept constant in order to represent the instantaneous linear elastic response of the model as observed in experiments.

In order to account for the stress dependent parameters, an iterative predictor-corrector approach was implemented in the UMAT subroutine. At the beginning of each UMAT run, a trial stress increment is calculated under consideration of the model parameters from the former time step. Based on the trial stress, the model parameters are updated and the trial stress increment is calculated backwards to an equivalent trial strain increment $\Delta \underline{\epsilon}_{tr}$ using the updated parameters. Now, the strain increment provided by the FE code $\Delta \underline{\epsilon}$ is subtracted from the trial strain increment and a residual $\Delta \underline{\epsilon}_{res}$ is formed. The residual is then minimized by an iterative Newton-Raphson algorithm until a trial stress is found which satisfies the convergence criterion (3).

$$\frac{\|\Delta \underline{\epsilon}_{res}\|}{\|\Delta \underline{\epsilon}\|} \leq 1 \cdot 10^{-6} \quad (3)$$

3 Results

3.1 Microstructure modeling

Table 1 gives an overview about the four generated RVE variants. Aim of the study is to keep the FOD and volume fraction almost constant while incorporating various FLD.

Table 1. Overview about the analyzed RVE variants

RVE	Dim. [mm ³]	v_f [%]	Elements
1 – random	5 x 5 x 0.181	12.99	$4.8 \cdot 10^6$
2 – measured	5 x 5 x 0.265	12.92	$7.0 \cdot 10^6$
3 – AR 10	5 x 5 x 0.109	13.09	$3.2 \cdot 10^6$
4 – AR 100	5 x 5 x 0.278	13.10	$7.3 \cdot 10^6$

RVE 1 features a so-called random FLD resulting from a former version of the fiber generator tool which did not take into account a specified FLD. Thus, the start points of the fiber extrusion vectors are distributed randomly in the RVE base area and fibers have been cut at the RVE borders.

RVE 2 incorporates a measured FLD determined by the company IDM Systems [4].

RVE 3 represents a uniform FLD with an aspect ratio (AR) of 10 (fiber length 0.17 mm) which is typical for a traditional short fiber reinforced composite.

RVE 4 is based on a uniform FLD with AR 100 (fiber length 1.7 mm) which is close to LFT.

All RVE variants exhibit a fiber volume fraction close to the calculated value of 13.22 % from measured mass flow rates during manufacturing.

In Fig. 5 the experimental two dimensional FOD from computer tomography (CT) analysis of a characteristic LFT specimen is compared to that of the investigated RVE variants. The 2D FOD have been determined by image correlation for both CT and RVE data in order to be comparable as described in [1]. They represent an integrated value over the analyzed specimen / RVE thickness with the thickness direction being normal to the fiber plane where the fibers of each layer do align. This simplification can be made because the layered structure is a direct consequence for values of fiber length which are significantly larger than the specimen thickness as it is the case for the investigated material. A CT scan of a characteristic LFT specimen is shown in Fig. 6 with the arrow marking the 0° direction of Fig. 5. The RVE distributions shown in Fig. 5 are mostly in good agreement to the experimental one.

Fig. 5. In-plane fiber orientation distributions of CT scan / FE-Mesh

Fig. 6. CT scan of a characteristic LFT specimen

Fig. 7,8 (9,10) show the FLD for RVE 1 (RVE 2) normalized by amount / volume. For the measured distribution, fibers longer than 4.7 mm have been cut to 4.7 mm to fit inside the RVE base area of $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$. The resulting peak is marked by an arrow in Fig. 9/10. The original experimental data exhibits a maximum fiber length of approx. 50 mm which could not be implemented into the structures analyzed in this work due to computational cost.

Fig. 7. FLD for RVE 1 (random) norm. by amount

Fig. 8. FLD for RVE 1 (random) norm. by volume

Fig. 9. FLD for RVE 2 (measured) norm. by amount

Fig. 10. FLD for RVE 2 (measured) norm. by vol.

Care must be taken while interpreting the FLD especially for distributions normalized by amount. Fig. 9 indicates that the majority of fibers exhibits a length well below 1 mm whereas the amount of longer fibers might be negligible. The same distribution normalized by volume - or total incorporated fiber length due to the constant fiber cross section - depicted in Fig. 10 reveals that 20% of the total fiber length of RVE 2 are assigned to a value of 4.7 mm and the section between 1 mm and 4.7 mm is at least the same volume fraction as the section below 1 mm.

In Fig. 11-14, cuttings of the fiber network (matrix elements are blinded out) of all RVE variants are depicted with dimensions of approx. $2.5 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm} \times \text{RVE thickness}$. Because of the different thicknesses of the RVEs, it seems that the structures are not equally dense. Actually, this is not the case as the values for fiber volume fraction deviate only negligibly (Table 1).

Fig. 11. RVE 1 (top: fiber plane, bottom: cross sect.)
The arrow marks the 0° direction (Fig. 5, 6).

Fig. 12. RVE 2 (top: fiber plane, bottom: cross sect.)
The arrow marks the 0° direction (Fig. 5, 6).

Fig. 13. RVE 3 (top: fiber plane, bottom: cross sect.)
The arrow marks the 0° direction (Fig. 5, 6).

Fig. 14. RVE 4 (top: fiber plane, bottom: cross sect.)
The arrow marks the 0° direction (Fig. 5, 6).

3.2 Viscoelastic matrix properties

Uniaxial creep and recovery tests of a period of $6 \cdot 10^5$ s each were carried out with matrix substance specimens from DOW® C711-70RNA polypropylene resin containing all additives and stabilizers used in the composite. Fig. 15 shows the Burgers model response (equation 1), fitted to each of the investigated stress levels. A strong nonlinear dependency on stress is observed which can be described through the stress dependent parameters of the modified Burgers model shown in Fig. 16 to 18 as symbols. The solid lines show the logarithmic functions which are implemented into the material subroutine in order to express the stress dependence. The dashed lines represent a second set of functions which corresponds to a virtually softened material behavior. This is needed to account for effects of mesh dependency described in section 3.3.

The instantaneous stiffness represented through the parameter E_0 is set to 1310 MPa for the original material and to 1050 MPa for the softened material, respectively.

Fig. 15. Burgers model fitted to creep tests of polypropylene matrix substance specimens under varying stress levels

Fig. 16. Stress dependence of E_1 and fit curves (solid line original, dashed line softened)

Fig. 17. Stress dependence of η_0 and fit curves (solid line original, dashed line softened)

Fig. 18. Stress dependence of η_1 and fit curves (solid line original, dashed line softened)

3.3 Viscoelastic composite properties

Creep simulations of a load period of $6 \cdot 10^5$ s were carried out for 0° and 90° orientation relative to mean fiber direction (peak in Fig. 5) at different stress levels (10, 30, 50 MPa in 0° and 7.5 MPa in 90° direction). Because of the complexity of the structure, no periodic boundary conditions were used and therefore stress and strain localizations result at the RVE borders where the displacement governing boundary conditions / the load is applied.

In order to determine the effective properties of the RVE, a free measure length was defined by two node sets in analogy to the experimental procedure where the strain is measured by an extensometer. Fig. 19 shows the definition of the node sets which are outside the heavily deformed region at the RVE border. The picture shows the v. Mises equivalent strain in the matrix elements for the highest investigated stress level of 50 MPa.

Fig. 19. Contour plot of v. Mises equivalent strain (deformation scale factor 5), definition of node sets

Fig. 20 to 22 compare microstructural creep simulations with creep experiments of LFT specimens for 0° orientation. In general, all three RVEs with fiber lengths related to LFT (RVE 1, 2 and 4) are in moderate to good agreement with the experiments. RVE 3 with AR 10 is far too compliant and the short fibers are obviously not able to slow the creep down as the longer fibers in the real material do. RVE 2 with the measured FLD features the best accordance to the experiments at all investigated stress levels. For 10 and 50 MPa, the deviation is within the experimental measurement error of approx. 0.001 absolute strain. The larger

deviation at 30 MPa stress level is likely because of experimental scatter. RVE 1 and 4 are also within the experimental measurement error for the lowest stress but behave significantly too stiff for higher loads. It is remarkable that the creep rate of RVE 4 is higher than that of RVE 1 and 2 but its strain at the beginning of the load period is lower than that of RVE 2. In general, the same arrangement of all creep curves can be observed for all stress levels, but the differences increase with increasing load. In 90° orientation where much less fibers are aligned in load direction, the differences between the RVEs are less significant and all LFT RVEs (1, 2, 4) are in the range of the experimental measurement error (Fig. 23). Only RVE 3 with AR 10 shows a remarkable deviation from the experiment.

Fig. 20. RVE simulation results and creep experiment for 0° orientation and 10 MPa stress

Fig. 21. RVE simulation results and creep experiment for 0° orientation and 30 MPa stress

Fig. 22. RVE simulation results and creep experiment for 0° orientation and 50 MPa stress

Fig. 23. RVE simulation results and creep experiment for 90° orientation and 7.5 MPa stress

In order to be able to analyze RVEs which contain a significant part of the real FLD and thus the here presented relatively large structures of 5 x 5 mm² base area and up to 10 million elements, the fibers can only be modeled with a single quadrilateral, linear element over the cross section and the matrix with linear tetrahedral elements for computational performance reasons. Therefore mesh convergence is not reached and strain localizations might not be displayed correctly because of the numerically inexpensive elements with linear approach resulting in a constant strain field within the element. In order to analyze the mesh dependency, a smaller structure of 1 x 1 x 0.1 mm³ (approx. 0.15 million elements) was meshed with a single linear quadrilateral element, 16 linear quadrilateral elements and 2 quadratic tetrahedral elements per fiber cross section,

which was kept square. The tetrahedral matrix elements remained linear for both fiber variants with linear elements and were changed to quadratic elements for the variant with quadratic fiber elements. No difference can be observed for the fine linear and the coarse quadratic mesh which means that convergence is reached for both variants. The deviation of the coarse linear, non-converged mesh (1 linear quadrilateral element with reduced integration) from the converged mesh is approx. 8% in instantaneous stiffness. As a consequence, the matrix behavior was softened until only negligible deviation of the creep curves could be observed between the coarse, non-converged mesh in combination with the softened material data and the converged mesh with the original material data for two different structures and two different stress levels. The comparison between the different mesh variants and the calibration of the softened material behavior is shown in Fig. 24 for one exemplary structure at the highest stress level.

Fig. 24. Comparison between different mesh variants of a small RVE ($1 \times 1 \times 0.1 \text{ mm}^3$, 0.15 million elements) and a stress level of 50 MPa

The resulting softened matrix behavior is shown as dashed lines in Fig. 16 to 18. Fig. 20 to 23 incorporate the softened matrix behavior in combination with the coarse mesh. In Fig. 25, the creep curves of RVE 2 and 3 are shown for 0° orientation and 50 MPa load for both original and softened material data using the coarse mesh as only option for the large RVEs ($5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ base area) due to computational cost. It can be observed that almost

no difference results for the LFT structure of RVE 2 whereas the deviation is significant for RVE 3 with AR 10. In the worst case, softened and original results might act as upper and lower bounds for the creep curves of RVE 3. However, the meaningfulness of the studies of Fig. 20 to 23 is ensured.

Fig. 25. Comparison of original (solid) and softened (dashed) material data for RVE 2 and 3

In Table 2, the elastic moduli of the analyzed structures are compared to experimental values from quasi static tensile tests on an electro mechanical testing machine. They represent the mean value of at least three valid specimens. For 0° orientation, RVE 2 which exhibits the best accordance to the creep curves shows an instantaneous stiffness of 5985 MPa which is significantly too low compared to the experimental value of 7834 MPa. On the other hand, RVE 1 which behaves too stiff in the creep experiments shows the best match to the experimental elastic stiffness for 0° orientation. A part of the deviation in stiffness of RVE 2 might be caused by the FOD which is slightly not sharp enough and therefore results in a too high amount of fibers between $+30$ and $+80^\circ$ (Fig. 5). This corresponds to the fact that RVE 2 features a higher elastic stiffness for 90° direction compared to RVE 1.

Table 2. Instantaneous elastic moduli

RVE	E_{11} [MPa]	E_{22} [MPa]
1 – random	7367	2344
2 – measured	5985	2706
3 – AR 10	3574	1879
4 – AR 100	7212	2417
Experimental	7834	3251

Another explanation is that the RVE edge length of 5 mm is still too small to consider the effects of the longest fibers which are up to about 50 mm in reality. However, analysis of the Halpin-Tsai equations [5] for a virtual unidirectional composite shows that 90% of the stiffness saturation value is reached for an AR below 300 which is the corresponding value for 5 mm fiber length (Fig. 26). Therefore it seems more likely that the measured FLD of RVE 2 might not contain enough long fibers to explain the experimentally determined elastic stiffness. Although the automatic scanning and analysis procedure to determine the FLD [4] can be considered as reliable, the results still depend on manual selection of several fiber batches which might distort the analysis.

Fig. 26. Halpin-Tsai [5] plot for $v_f = 0.13$, $E_{\text{Matrix}} = 1400 \text{ MPa}$, $E_{\text{Fiber}} = 72000 \text{ MPa}$

If RVE 1 is considered as more realistic because of the better fit in instantaneous stiffness, another time-dependent, inelastic deformation mechanism must be existent besides the pure viscoelastic matrix behavior, as the creep response of RVE 1 is significantly too stiff.

A reasonable assumption might be the presence of successive interface damage during the creep load period.

In the following study, cohesive zone elements (thickness $0.01 \mu\text{m}$) with a simplified mechanical behavior governed by a traction-separation law without coupling between normal and shear components of the elastic stiffness matrix

(equation 4) have been implemented in between fiber and matrix elements.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_n \\ \sigma_s \\ \sigma_t \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_n & & \\ & K_s & \\ & & K_t \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_n \\ \varepsilon_s \\ \varepsilon_t \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The indices n, s and t refer to the normal, the first shear and second shear direction, respectively. The stiffness coefficients K have been chosen to a sufficiently high value so that the elastic response of the RVE with implemented cohesive zones but without considering cohesive damage has not changed significantly compared to the original RVE without cohesive elements.

A quadratic damage initiation criterion (5) was used, being $\sigma_{n, s, t}$ the stress and $\sigma_{n, s, t}^{\text{max}}$ the strength in normal, first and second shear direction, respectively. The $\langle \rangle$ operator effects that no normal pressure stresses will cause any damage. The values for $\sigma_{n, s, t}^{\text{max}}$ have always been set equally to the referred values in the following study.

$$\left(\frac{\langle \sigma_n \rangle}{\sigma_n^{\text{max}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_s^{\text{max}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_t^{\text{max}}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

For the description of damage evolution, a linear softening, energy-based approach was chosen. The scalar damage variable D with an initial value of 0 corresponding to undamaged state increases linear with nodal displacement after damage initiation until it reaches a maximum value of 1. The current stresses $\sigma_{n, s, t}$ are related to the undamaged stresses $\sigma_{n, s, t}^0$ after (6):

$$\sigma_{n, s, t} = (1 - D)\sigma_{n, s, t}^0 \quad (6)$$

Again, negative normal stresses have no effect. The softening continues until the value for the element's fracture energy, calculated by the FE-code from the specified energy release rate, is reached. No mode-dependency of damage evolution has been specified.

Reference values for the interface shear strength of 13.5 to 18 MPa and for the energy release rate of 2.96 to 4.7 J/m² are taken from [6], [7] for glass fiber / polypropylene composites.

It needs to be emphasized that only little information about manufacturing conditions and matrix constituents (i.e. exact polymer formulation, use of stabilizers or coupling agents) is available for the literature values. Thus they can only be treated as a rough estimation because the interface properties can vary significantly for different constitutions and fabrication conditions of the polymeric matrix system. Nevertheless, the literature data is helpful as a reference to carry out a parametric study to incorporate interface damage into the microstructural model and to give an estimation of the role of interface effects with respect to the creep behavior of LFT.

Because of the complexity of the model, not the full RVEs could be analyzed. Therefore, a stripe of $0.5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ was cut from RVE 1 with the long side parallel to the mean fiber direction and only the very beginning of the load period until at maximum 10000 s was analyzed. Fig. 27 to 30 show the creep behavior for varying interface properties (strength, energy release rate) of the cropped variant of RVE 1 which is called RVE 1* from now on.

As many fibers have been cropped at the cutting line, the overall compliance of RVE 1* (without cohesive elements) is somewhat increased compared to the response of the original, $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ sized RVE 1. To improve the readability of the data, all creep curves of RVE 1* have been offset by the difference in strain between RVE 1 and RVE 1* without cohesive elements. Thus the solid reference curve of RVE 1* without implemented damage is almost equal to the response of the original, plain variant of RVE 1.

Fig. 27 shows that the literature value for the interface energy release rate of approx. 5 J/m^2 results in significantly too compliant material behavior for interface strength values of 15 – 35 MPa. Because in reality, a fraction of the damage evolution energy release rate also originates from post damage friction between fibers and matrix, which cannot be incorporated separately into the model, it seems to be appropriate to increase the value for the interface energy release rate. Fig. 28 to 30 consider values of 10 – 20 J/m^2 . The results are in general more reasonable. In detail, values of 15 J/m^2 (interface strength chosen to 10 MPa) and 20 J/m^2 (7.5 MPa) yield the best match to the shape of the experimental

creep curve. The discontinuous slope of some curves is likely because of numerical discretization effects.

Fig. 27. Creep properties of RVE 1* for various interfacial strength values and an energy release rate of 5 J/m^2

Fig. 28. Creep properties of RVE 1* for various interfacial strength values and an energy release rate of 10 J/m^2

Fig. 29. Creep properties of RVE 1* for various interfacial strength values and an energy release rate of 15 J/m^2

Fig. 30. Creep properties of RVE 1* for various interfacial strength values and an energy release rate of 20 J/m²

In Fig. 31, the two best performing variants of the short-time screening presented in Fig. 27 to 30 with interface properties of 10 MPa / 15 J/m² and 7.5 MPa / 20 J/m² have been analyzed for a longer time period. It can be observed that above 10000 s, their behavior is significantly too compliant and thus the interface strength values are likely chosen somewhat too low. Future long-time simulations will be helpful to determine the interface properties more precisely.

Fig. 31. Longer analyzed time period for the two best performing variants of Fig. 27 to 30

Finally, the parametric study shows that interface properties close to literature (numerical 7.5 to 10 MPa / 15 to 20 J/m², reference 13.5 to 18 MPa / 2.96 to 4.7 J/m²) can explain the deviation of some microstructural simulations from experimental results.

It seems to be reasonable that the numerically fitted values for energy release rate are significantly higher than the reference values because they also need to represent an additional part of post damage friction which is not implemented separately. In the end, the studies support the assumption that interface properties need to be considered for the investigated material at least for higher load levels.

Fig. 32 shows a fracture surface of a LFT specimen which was frozen by liquid nitrogen to conserve the microstructure and to avoid energy-consuming deformation during fracture. A high amount of fiber pull-out can be observed which can be interpreted as another indication that significant interface effects will likely occur during mechanical deformation of the composite.

Fig. 32. Fracture surface of a characteristic LFT specimen frozen by liquid nitrogen (scanning electron microscopy)

4 Conclusions

A microstructure-based approach to evaluate the creep behavior of long fiber reinforced thermoplastics was presented. Because of the numerical efficient description of the structure with a coarse finite element mesh, large structures which incorporate a significant part of the experimentally determined fiber length spectrum which features a maximum fiber length of approx. 50 mm can be analyzed in a reasonable time. Element studies of smaller structures show that although the coarse mesh needs to be used with care, the discretization

error is relatively weak and the method can be considered as promising to analyze even larger structures as the ones presented here.

The time-dependent deformation of the polypropylene matrix was incorporated by a modified Burgers model which was calibrated with creep tests of matrix substance specimens. In general, a good agreement between the results of micromechanical simulations and experimental creep tests of composite specimens could be observed for simulations which incorporate a fiber length related to long fiber reinforcements and a experimentally determined fiber orientation distribution. A strong influence of fiber length on the creep properties could be observed while comparing different virtual fiber length distributions. Large uncertainties still remain with respect to the experimental determination of the fiber length distribution as the analyzed fiber batches were selected manually which might distort the results.

For higher stress levels, interface damage likely occurs in the LFT structures. A parametric study shows that interface properties which are close to values from literature for an arbitrary polypropylene/glass fiber system can explain the deviation between microstructural simulations and creep experiments for the highest investigated load level.

5 Outlook

Larger RVEs with a non-square base section - e.g. 25 to 50 mm length and 1 to 2 mm width - will be generated to take into account almost the complete spectrum of fiber lengths from experimental analysis (at maximum approx. 50 mm).

Recent results of a two-part analysis, where the fiber lattice is first screened, the long fiber fraction is weighted and manually analyzed and only the short fiber fraction is analyzed by the automated procedure show a significantly higher amount of long fibers than the presently used length distribution. This will be considered for a new set of RVE studies and can be rated as promising to yield more realistic results.

Furthermore, sub-models will be generated to analyze the influence of fiber length and interface properties more systematically incorporating detailed FE meshes. By this means, the deviation of the coarse representation of the fibers with a quadrilateral cross section from the round section in reality can be evaluated and quantified.

References

- [1] S. Fliegner, M. Luke, M. Reif, "Microstructure-based modeling of the creep behavior of long-fiber-reinforced thermoplastics", *Proceedings of 15th European Conference on Composite Materials*, Venice, 2012
- [2] J. Lai, A. Bakker, "3-D schapery representation for non-linear viscoelasticity and finite element implementation", *Computational Mechanics*, Vol. 18, pp 182-191, 1996
- [3] M.F. Woldekidan, "Response Modelling of Bitumen, Bituminous Mastic and Mortar", Dissertation, Delft University of Technology, 2011, ISBN 978-90-8570-762-2
- [4] IDM Systems, <http://www.idm-systems.de>, 30.01.13
- [5] J.C. Halpin, J.L. Kardos, "The Halpin-Tsai Equations: A review", *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol. 16, 1976
- [6] S. Zhandarov, E. Maeder, "Characterization of fiber/matrix interface strength: applicability of different tests, approaches and parameters", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 65, pp 149-160, 2005
- [7] S. Zhandarov, E. Pisanova, E. Maeder, "Is there any contradiction between the stress and energy failure criteria in micromechanical tests?", *Journal of adhesion science and technology*, Vol. 19, pp 679-704, 2005

Acknowledgement

The authors appreciate the financial support from the KITE hyLITE innovation cluster funded by the Fraunhofer Gesellschaft, the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and the state of Baden-Württemberg.